

Voltage Harmonic Mitigation by Distributed Renewable Energy Sources in Low-Voltage Distribution Networks: Sensitivity Analysis

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Abstract—The ever-growing penetration of converter-interfaced distributed renewable energy sources (CI-DRES) combined with the presence of non-linear loads (NLLs) might generate serious power quality issues in distribution networks (DNs). Currently, numerous approaches have been proposed for CI-DRES voltage source converters (VSCs) to operate as active harmonic filters; however, most of them mitigate the problem locally without investigating which CI-DRES in the DN would be most appropriate to perform such service. In this paper, a sensitivity analysis is conducted, and a mathematical framework is formulated to assess and quantify the contribution of each CI-DRES to the decentralized harmonic filtering process in a low-voltage (LV) DN with the presence of NLLs based on the location and available capacity of each CI-DRES. The latter is a crucial element since, in the future, the CI-DRES may offer various services simultaneously, e.g., reactive power or virtual inertia. The proposed framework and analysis are verified via simulations in the time domain and via decoupled harmonic power flows considering the benchmark CIGRE LV DN and the IEEE European LV Test feeder under various mixtures of CI-DRES/NLLs. The conclusions will pave the way so that active filtering is treated as a new ancillary service that CI-DRES can offer and it can be introduced in relevant markets.

Index Terms—Active filters, Ancillary Service, Distributed Generation, Harmonic Mitigation

I. INTRODUCTION

THE path to decarbonisation necessitates greater penetration and dependence on low-carbon generation, storage and demand technologies, the majority of which are interfaced to the electric grid via power electronics (PE), [1], [2]. The growing penetration of converter interfaced distributed renewable energy sources (CI-DRES) has already posed several challenges to the distribution networks (DNs), e.g. voltage regulation issues, contingency, reverse power flows, power quality problems, [3]–[5]. In addition, massive harmonic injection can occur by non-linear loads (NLLs), e.g., AC/DC rectifiers in Electric Vehicles (EVs), led lighting, variable-speed drives, and nonlinear home appliances, [6], [7]. This situation leads in

turn to detrimental impacts on the DN's equipment and loads, [3]–[5], [8], e.g., overload of the neutral wires, overheating, electromagnetic and communication interference, etc. The combined effect of dispersed residential NLLs has resulted in harmonic current distortion levels in residential feeders that are higher than those in industrial and commercial feeders, [6]. As a result, excessive voltage harmonic distortion (HD) in residential DN's is a developing challenge that utilities will have to deal with in the near future.

International Standards and national grid codes mandate that the harmonic content of the DN's be kept below certain thresholds [4] for frequencies up to 2kHz. For example, IEEE Std 519-2022 [4] and IEC 61000-3-6 standards, [9] set limits for individual and total HD of the CI-DRES voltage and current at its point of common coupling (PCC) with the grid. On the plus side, the increased controllability of the voltage source converters (VSCs) that link the CI-DRES with the DN can be used to reduce HD, [1], [10]. Thereby, in addition to active power, the CI-DRES may inject regulated harmonic components in order to improve power quality in the DN.

A. Literature Review

Up to now, several research studies deal with the presence of voltage and current harmonics in DN's and their mitigation. Generally, these studies can be classified considering the following topics:

(i) the influence of CI-DRES penetration and NLLs on DN's, which limit CI-DRES Hosting Capacity (HC) and permissible CI-DRES penetration in light of HD limits: In [11], the impact of the CI-DRES generated HD components on the HC of DN's is analysed considering the limits prescribed in the IEEE 519 Std. In [12] the significance of integrating HD limits in the HC assessment is stressed out. In [13] the Harmonic-Constrained HC term is used to emphasize that the power system HC can be estimated by considering solely the voltage HD limits.

(ii) the Supraharmonics: A particular topic that has emerged with the presence of CI-DRES, NLLs, and bi-directional EVs [14], [15] is the presence of voltage and current harmonic disturbances in a frequency range 2-500 kHz, generally known as supraharmonic emissions (SEs). The SEs might be low at nominal VSC power. However, at low power levels the opposite conditions might occur since the SEs remain stable independent of the VSC loading, [14], [15]. The effects of SEs are discussed in [14]–[16], e.g., thermal stress and power

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losses in electronic equipment, problems related to power line communications.

(iii) the optimal size and location for the installation of passive filters considering the limits on the DN HC. Specifically, single-tuned passive harmonic filters have been designed in [17]–[20] to be located in industrial systems with NLLs with the aim to minimize the DN average voltage total HD (THD_V) based on the fundamental-frequency power flow (FFPF) and on Decoupled Harmonic Power Flows (DHPFs). The optimal filter sizing is solved as mixed integer optimization problem considering total and individual HD percentages. In [21] the optimal allocation of distributed passive filters is proposed in a microgrid that contains CI-DRES and NLLs.

(iv) active filtering (AF) control techniques and the operation of CI-DRES as active power filters (APFs): These methods are decentralized, i.e., it is assumed that the voltage HD is a phenomenon that should be mitigated locally. In [22] it is suggested that CI-DRES could provide harmonic mitigation as an ancillary service (AS) without additional purchase costs if its apparent power is sufficient. In this way, the installation of large-scale central APFs could be avoided, since they are an expensive solution. The CI-DRES AF control approaches are categorized as follows, [22]:

- virtual impedance-based methods: a virtual impedance (resistance, [23], [24] or conductance, [10], [25]) can emulate the effect of physical impedance without the need to connect a real component to a system.
- active harmonic filtering-based methods, where the main objective is to produce an appropriate compensating current in the VSC.

Recent studies aim at eliminating the current harmonics at unit level, [26] with full-feedforward Techniques, [27] and active front end configurations, [28]. At system level [26], the Harmonic Mitigation Function has been proposed in [29] which mitigates harmonics generated by motor drives. In addition, since APFs need to closely follow the reference current and quickly inject the necessary currents into the grid to reduce harmonics, sliding mode control has been suggested to mitigate uncertainties, [26].

(v) Harmonic State Estimation (HSE) Methods, [26], [30], [31]: Power quality monitoring is an emerging issue for DN Operators (DNOs), while collecting, recording and storing power quality data are main challenges. A recent topic towards this direction is the development of HSE methods with the aim of determining the optimal number of instruments and deployment locations, or managing power quality parameters, [26]. In [30] a HSE algorithm is proposed for identifying the harmonic sources in DNs based on data from different measuring devices, like Smart meters, Power Quality Analyzers and transformer terminal units. In [31] the HSE method is based on graph signal processing.

B. Identified Gaps

Based on the aforementioned research works, some drawbacks and gaps have been identified.

With respect to SEs, there exist a gap with respect to their proper measurement and definition. Above 2 kHz up to 150

kHz, no standards defining SEs limits currently exist (except for power-electronic devices related to lighting, [14]–[16]). In the control of CI-DRES and EVs VSCs switching frequencies up to 40 kHz are used [14], [15], thus, CI-DRES and EVs become SE sources. Currently, it is impossible to eliminate SEs with AF techniques from other VSCs, since the latter would be required to operate at very high switching frequencies, i.e. larger than 300kHz. Frequencies of such order currently are used only for inductive power transfer (wireless EV charging stations), [14], [15]. For the conventional conductive power transfer, this order of frequencies is prohibitive since they would increase the power/energy losses and the VSC loses its controllability. Therefore, it would be recommended that no therapeutic action takes place, i.e., mitigation of SEs by AFs. Instead, focus should be paid on the proper design of the filter components and the control of the CI-DRES so that they do not exhibit SEs.

Regarding the HSE methods, different issues have been identified, e.g., the collection of data from measuring devices of different resolution, [30]. Another issue is that the number of state variables in the HSE methods may exceed the number of measurements, even when all the available data are utilized; thus, the state equation will be underdetermined, [30], [31]. The observability of the DN can be enhanced, when the locations of harmonic sources are known, because the variables related to buses without harmonic sources can be removed from the state equation.

With respect to the utilization of a central active or passive filter at power system level proposed in [17], [18], [20], [23], [32], the following disadvantages have been identified [17]: (a) possible parallel resonance of the filter with other electrical components of the DNs; (b) after their sizing the voltage and current of the filter elements should be checked to avoid any adverse increase in their rating compared to their fundamental rating. In a possible failure of the filter, the AF could lead to the “whack-a-mole” effect, [23], [33], where the mitigation of one harmonic frequency voltage (HFV) could lead to the increase of another HFV. To avoid the whack-a-mole effect, the HD in multi-bus electric grids may be mitigated by connecting an APF to each node, [32].

Despite the plethora of studies with respect to the control of APFs, [26]–[28], there are still significant gaps in addressing HD within DNs. Recently issued Standards, e.g. [34], [35], have provided specifications for the operation of CI-DRES under the exchange of reactive power (RP) for voltage regulation. The untapped capacity of the CI-DRES can be exploited to provide harmonic mitigation as an AS that could be tradable in specific AS markets. Nevertheless, the harmonic mitigation as an AS to be offered by the CI-DRES needs to be co-evaluated along with other AS keeping in mind that the CI-DRES may exceed its thermal capacity. Until now, most of the AF methods rely on local controllers without considering the effects in the rest of the DN and without examining which CI-DRES within the DN would be most suitable to provide such service. Hence, the AF operation by CI-DRES has been treated in a local decentralized manner, i.e., the CI-DRES close to a NLL should compensate the low-order harmonic emissions of the NLL. This action is similar

to decentralized voltage regulation approaches. The sensitivity of a CI-DRES location with respect to the NLL low-order harmonic frequencies (HFVs) at DN level has not been studied yet in the technical literature. Consequently, when performing a decentralized harmonic mitigation control, the contribution of a CI-DRES needs to be quantified considering the CI-DRES location (with respect to the NLL or within the DN) and in terms of its thermal capacity.

C. Paper Contribution

This paper attempts to fill the identified gaps related to the APF control and CI-DRES contribution as follows: A mathematical framework is formulated towards the evaluation of the sensitivity of the CI-DRES location within a LV DN under the presence of NLLs. This framework provides a further insight on the quantification of the contribution of each CI-DRES in the AF process considering the CI-DRES thermal capacity as a parameter. As it is evident in [11], [36], [37] the most prevailing voltage harmonics within DNs are the low-order ones, i.e., 5^{th} , 7^{th} , 11^{th} , 13^{th} . In order to respect the CI-DRES thermal limit and not overload the CI-DRES with higher order HFVs, in [25] and [24] decentralized virtual conductance and resistance approaches respectively have been proposed to mitigate simultaneously the above HFVs within DNs, thus, avoiding the “whack-a-mole” effect. In this paper, the sensitivity analysis is performed considering these HFVs in order to quantify the contribution of each CI-DRES to the decentralized APF process. The sensitivity analysis is based on two calculation approaches: the Power Definition approach based on the IEEE 1459-2010 Standard and the Harmonic Impedance approach. Note that this analysis considers balanced conditions, while unbalances are out of scope in this work and will be considered in future works.

The framework is evaluated via two types of simulations: DHPFs in OpenDSS Software Package and Time Domain (TD) simulations in PowerSim (PSIM) Software Package. In the latter, the AF virtual conductance approach proposed in [25] is modelled in detail. It is noted that a comparison between DHPFs and TD simulations is performed with respect to low-order HFVs at each node, with and without the AF control. No such comparison between DHPFs and TD simulations has been found in the technical literature. The results prove that there exist CI-DRES which are more critical during the APF process, hence, they may exhaust their capacity compared to others within the same LV DN.

Finally, it is important to highlight that this paper has the following contributions with respect to [1]:

(1) Additional simulation results both in the TD and via DHPFs: Specifically, in [1] the simulations were conducted in the CIGRE Benchmark European Residential LV DN, while in this paper, further simulations are conducted in the IEEE European LV Test Feeder. The latter is more sensitive to power variations, and has been widely used in voltage quality studies, [38]. This specific topology together with the NLL type used in the simulations have caused the outburst of the “whack-a-mole” effect, i.e., the mitigation of the 5^{th} and 11^{th} HFVs has caused the increase of the 7^{th} and 13^{th} HFVs. Yet, it is

clearly demonstrated that the deactivation of the control in the 7^{th} and 13^{th} harmonics might lead to detrimental performance compared to the case where all HFVs are mitigated.

(2) In [1] the sensitivity analysis was performed assuming only the Power Definition approach. Here, the sensitivity analysis is conducted also considering the harmonic impedance approach. These two approaches are compared, in order to evaluate if the sensitivity analysis based on the harmonic impedance approach can achieve similar results with less computational complexity.

The rest of the manuscript is organised as follows: Section II provides a brief overview of the methodology to be followed and its individual components. Section III presents the theoretical background and mathematical framework for the sensitivity analysis. Section IV presents the simulation models in the TD and the DHPFs. In Section V simulation results are presented to demonstrate the validity of the framework. Finally, Section VI closes the paper with its main findings and proposes new directions for further research.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Background

During the past decade, several European countries have incorporated voltage quality monitoring programs in their DNs, as mentioned in the recent 7th CEER-ECRB Benchmarking Report on the Quality of Electricity and Gas Supply [39]. In many countries like Austria, Belgium, Cyprus, etc., the end-users are able to file complaints to the DNOs if they notice any malfunction of devices due to poor power and voltage quality and they are allowed to install their own power quality analyzers. In these cases, financial compensation is anticipated to the customers who suffer from poor power and voltage quality (Germany, France, etc), either by the DNOs or by end-users who possess NLLs and pollute the DN, [39]. With the increasing penetration of NLLs and CI-DRES at all voltage levels, the DNOs should increase their observability and gain full awareness of their DN topology, otherwise, they would bear increased costs related to poor voltage quality.

The majority of the power quality analyzers currently owned by the DNOs, [40], [41], like [42], measure the average power quantities at different HFVs based on the IEEE 1459:2010 Standard, [43].

Based on the above remarks, in this paper, it is considered that the DNO possesses a measuring system for HFVs and HF currents at each low-order HF (**$h=5,7,11,13$**), especially at nodes where there are relatively large installations of NLLs (more than 5kVA), e.g., six-pulse rectifiers. In addition, it is assumed that the DN line impedances and configuration are readily available to the DNO. It is noted that fast-dynamic voltage disturbances are not taken into account, similar to [44], [45]. The respective calculations are assumed to be under steady-state conditions, e.g., every 1 minute.

B. Practical Implementation

The methodology proposed in this paper can be easily implemented in the frame of a smart grid for the following reasons:

(i) The proposed APF algorithm can be easily introduced to the CI-DRES microprocessor, [46]. In terms of hardware, only slight modifications in the high frequency filter at the VSC output might be needed with insignificant cost increase.

(ii) Signals for the configuration of the APF in each CI-DRES can be sent via the communication channel between the DNO and the CI-DRES only every time the DN topology changes or a new CI-DRES/NLL is added.

(iii) Power quality data can be acquired (average values every 10 minutes are sufficient based on the EN 50160 Standard) from the CI-DRES and from the smart meters of the NLLs via the aforementioned smart-grid communication channel. In case this communication channel is absent, the DNO may configure manually each new CI-DRES just once prior to its installation, knowing however, that this is not the optimum set-up.

C. Proposed Methodology

In this paper, the sensitivity analysis is based on two calculation approaches: the Power Definition approach based on the IEEE 1459-2010 Standard and the Harmonic Impedance approach.

For the Harmonic Impedance approach, it is required that the DNOs has full knowledge of the DN under study with respect to the connecting lines/cables, i.e., R , L . Then, the harmonic impedance between any two nodes of the DN can be calculated at each low-order HF. In case NLLs are located at specific nodes, this approach could identify the most suitable nodes where CI-DRES with APF functionality should be installed, in order for the voltage THD to be reduced most efficiently.

For the Power Definition approach based on the IEEE 1459-2010 Standard, it is required that the DNOs possess power quality measuring devices at the NLL nodes. In such case, average power values with harmonic components can be readily available to them. Based on the acquired measurements, the DNOs are able to conduct DHPFs at every low-order HF without the need for detailed modelling of the NLLs. The results of the DHPFs can be used to perform sensitivity analysis using the Power Definition Approach to identify the most appropriate nodes to implement AF process by the local CI-DRES.

As it will be shown, using either sensitivity approach, the DNO will be able to identify the CI-DRES that is most likely to provide harmonic mitigation most efficiently. In this way, during the planning stage the DNO could allow an oversized CI-DRES VSC with respect to the CI-DRES primary source, so as to have more available capacity. The proposed framework can be used in two ways: (i) LV DN planning and CI-DRES sizing; (ii) development of a distributed harmonic mitigation control scheme based on the sensitivity matrix at each HF. This procedure has been already implemented in state-of-the-art voltage regulation methods, which employ the CI-DRES available RP, [45] or active power curtailment, [47].

The proposed framework to identify the most critical CI-DRES nodes able to act as APFs most efficiently is validated via TD simulations in the following manner: two LV DNs

are simulated which include detailed models of NLLs and CI-DRES VSCs. The latter are able to act as APFs based on the harmonic voltage detection at the PCC (instantaneous PQ theory, [33]), by incorporating a virtual conductance approach, [25] in each individual low-order HF, taking into account the CI-DRES thermal capacity. The CI-DRES that reaches first its thermal capacity is the most critical to provide the AF as AS.

In order to quantify the contribution of each CI-DRES in the AF process, power quality measuring devices need to be installed at the CI-DRES nodes as well. In this paper, a method for quantifying the contribution of each CI-DRES in a decentralized control scheme is discussed. If the contribution of each CI-DRES is quantified, the operational costs could be evaluated based on detailed cost-functions [48] and this AS could be remunerated in future respective markets.

III. SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

In this section, the mathematical formulation for the sensitivity analysis is described based on specific technical background reported in the state-of-the-art.

A. Proposed DN Modelling

This section presents the DN model which is used in the DHPFs and the power flow at the fundamental frequency f . The current flowing through the branch that connects node i with j is calculated as:

$$\bar{I}_{ij}^x = \bar{Y}_{ij}^x \bar{V}_{ij}^x \quad \forall x \in \{f, h\} \quad (1)$$

where \bar{V}_{ij}^x and \bar{I}_{ij}^x denote the complex voltage drop and the complex branch current between nodes i and j , respectively. The superscript x denotes the examined frequency that can be either f or a higher HF (h). The term \bar{Y}_{ij}^x stands for the series admittance of the line connecting node i with node j at the examined frequency x . The corresponding complex current at node i (\bar{I}_i^x) can be generally expressed as follows:

$$\bar{I}_i^x = \sum_{k \in N \setminus \{i\}} \bar{Y}_{ki}^x \bar{V}_k^x - \left(\sum_{k \in N \setminus \{i\}} \bar{Y}_{ki}^x \right) \bar{V}_i^x \quad (2)$$

where N is the set of the network nodes. At fundamental frequency f , (2) is transformed to the well-established power flow equations, [45]:

$$P_i = V_i \sum_{j \in N} V_j [G_{ij} \cos(\theta_i - \theta_j) + B_{ij} \sin(\theta_i - \theta_j)], \quad \forall i \in N \quad (3)$$

$$Q_i = V_i \sum_{j \in N} V_j [G_{ij} \sin(\theta_i - \theta_j) - B_{ij} \cos(\theta_i - \theta_j)], \quad \forall i \in N \quad (4)$$

where V_i and θ_i denote the magnitude and angle of the voltage node i , respectively. Furthermore, G_{ij} and B_{ij} are the real and imaginary part of the series admittance of the line that connects node i with node j . P_i and Q_i stand for the net injected active and RP at node i that are calculated according to

$$P_i = P_i^G - P_i^L \quad \forall i \in N \quad (5)$$

$$Q_i = Q_i^G - Q_i^L \quad \forall i \in N \quad (6)$$

where P_i^G , Q_i^G , P_i^L , and Q_i^L are the active and RP of the CI-DRES and load connected to node i , respectively. Based on this analysis, it is evident that CI-DRES and loads are modelled as constant PQ sources at f . Eqs. (3)-(6) are employed to model the power flow within the DN at f . The slack bus voltage is set to the rated DN voltage and with a zero angle reference. The shunt capacitances of the lines have been neglected at f due to their reduced influence at LV DNs.

Regarding the DHPFs, (2) and (7) are employed to model the DN at HF s . For the present analysis, it is assumed that the slack bus does not exhibit any HD_V , hence, at HF h , the voltage angle and magnitude of the slack bus are zero. With respect to the NLL modelling in LV DNs, in [49] four NLL types examined for harmonic analysis of residential loads with OpenDSS in the IEEE LV European Test Feeder: Norton, Norton with real voltage, Ideal Current Source and Mixed Model (linear load as an admittance and the NLLs as ideal current sources at HF s). It is concluded that when resonances are not present (something that is not expected in LV DNs at low-order HF s), all NLL models bring similar results, while the ideal current source one is less CPU intensive and simulations run faster in OpenDSS. Therefore, in this study, the NLLs are modelled as ideal current sources injecting harmonic currents to the DN.

In case of Medium Voltage (MV) DNs, e.g., [17], [18], shunt capacitors may exist on the system (e.g., lines). These shunt capacitors might cause resonances, hence, they should be taken into account in MV DNs. In this case, the current at node i at HF h (\bar{I}_i^h) can be calculated as follows:

$$\bar{I}_i^h = -jh\omega C_i V_i^h - \bar{I}_i^{L,h} \quad (7)$$

where ω is the angular frequency, C_i is the shunt capacitance and $\bar{I}_i^{L,h}$ is the h -th load harmonic current at node i . In such case, this quantity should be added in (2). In this study, the shunt capacitors of the lines are neglected also in HF s , since the study focuses on LV DNs, where the resistive nature of the lines is prevailing at low-order HF s .

The sensitivity matrix will be derived under the condition where the CI-DRES AF functionality is not activated. Thus, at a first stage, the CI-DRES harmonic content is set to zero in the DHPFs. At a second step, in order to evaluate the CI-DRES AF functionality, the CI-DRES are modelled as ideal current sources that inject harmonic currents with specific angle to the CI-DRES PCC.

B. Theoretical Background at Fundamental Frequency

Traditionally, the sensitivity matrix is calculated by inverting the Jacobian matrix used in the Newton-Raphson approach for grid power flow analysis, [45], [50]. In [45] the sensitivity analysis method was employed to obtain a quantitative evaluation of the CI-DRES active and RP variation impact on the variation of the voltage magnitude. From power flow analysis, the sensitivity matrix is given by:

$$\mathbf{S}_V = \mathbf{J}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \mathbf{P}} & \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \mathbf{Q}} \\ \frac{\partial |\mathbf{V}|}{\partial \mathbf{P}} & \frac{\partial |\mathbf{V}|}{\partial \mathbf{Q}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

In [47] the term $\frac{\partial |\mathbf{V}|}{\partial \mathbf{P}}$ is examined as submatrix, where each element is interpreted as the variation that would happen in the voltage profile at a certain bus i in the case of a hypothetical 1-pu variation in the injection of active power at bus j . In [45] the term $\frac{\partial |\mathbf{V}|}{\partial \mathbf{Q}}$ is used to quantify the impact of RP variations on the DN voltages. In this paper (8) is used for the sensitivity matrix calculation at f and then, it is adapted for the sensitivity matrix calculation at the HF s h .

C. Theoretical Framework based on the Power Definitions of the IEEE 1459:2010 Standard

The apparent power definition in the IEEE 1459-2010 Standard, [43], divides the apparent power to a fundamental component and a non-fundamental one. The latter can be divided into to three distinctive items:

$$S_N^2 = S_H^2 + D_I^2 + D_V^2 = \sum_{h \neq 1} V_h^2 \cdot \sum_{h \neq 1} I_h^2 + V_1^2 \cdot \sum_{h \neq 1} I_h^2 + I_1^2 \cdot \sum_{h \neq 1} V_h^2 \quad (9)$$

where the terms D_I and D_V imply the coupling between f and the HF s . The term S_H is the sum of all HF s ' powers except from f and is further expressed as:

$$S_H^2 = \sum_{h \neq 1} (V_h \cdot I_h)^2 = \sqrt{P_H^2 + D_H^2} \quad (10)$$

The term D_H refers to the distortion power of the combination of the HFVs and harmonic currents. Thus, D_H includes again the coupling among the different HF s except from f . On the other hand, the term P_H is the product of the voltage and current at the same HF. Thus, it is the only term that expresses the power carried by the HF s of the same order, and is not coupled with any other frequency, neither the fundamental one, nor the other HF s . Based on this analysis, P_H is going to be the power that is calculated at specific HF after the DHPF. The sensitivity matrix at each HF \mathbf{h} can be computed by inverting the Jacobian matrix calculated after the DHPF as:

$$\mathbf{S}_V^{\mathbf{h}} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \theta^{\mathbf{h}}}{\partial \mathbf{P}^{\mathbf{h}}} & \frac{\partial \theta^{\mathbf{h}}}{\partial \mathbf{Q}^{\mathbf{h}}} \\ \frac{\partial |\mathbf{V}^{\mathbf{h}}|}{\partial \mathbf{P}^{\mathbf{h}}} & \frac{\partial |\mathbf{V}^{\mathbf{h}}|}{\partial \mathbf{Q}^{\mathbf{h}}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

where $P_H = \mathbf{P}^{\mathbf{h}}$ and $\mathbf{V}^{\mathbf{h}}$ is the magnitude of the HFV. It is proposed that the harmonic active power sensitivity submatrix $\frac{\partial V_i^{\mathbf{h}}}{\partial P^{\mathbf{h}}}$ is isolated and calculated for the nodes of interest within a LV DN. Specifically, following a similar rationale for the fundamental frequency, this submatrix denotes that a variation of the CI-DRES term P_H located at node j , i.e., $\partial P_j^{\mathbf{h}}$, will cause a variation in the HFV of a NLL located at node i , i.e., $\partial V_i^{\mathbf{h}}$. Consequently, the CI-DRES at node j presenting a high $\frac{\partial V_i^{\mathbf{h}}}{\partial P_j^{\mathbf{h}}}$ will need to inject a smaller amount of low-order harmonic current at $HF = \mathbf{h}$ compared to a CI-DRES with a small sensitivity.

Based on the rationale for the fundamental frequency, [47], the following procedure is proposed to identify the most critical CI-DRES that will be mostly suitable to act as an

APF: For each harmonic the most critical CI-DRES node (CR-DRES) per harmonic is the one that has the maximum sum of submatrices:

$$\text{CR-DRES}^h = \text{MAX} \left[\sum_{\forall j \in N} \frac{\partial V_i^h}{\partial P_j^h} \right] \quad \forall i \in N \quad (12)$$

This means that for a specific voltage variation, the smallest amount of ∂P^h will be provided by the CR-DRES^h. This corresponds to the smallest amount of $|\bar{I}_{i,G}^h|$ (the CI-DRES harmonic current injection at $HF = h$ and node i). It can be expected that the CR-DRES^h are different per HF.

The total loading of the CI-DRES connected at node i with respect to its rated current shall be:

$$\frac{P_i^{f,G^2} + Q_i^{f,G^2}}{3V_i^{f^2}} + \sum_{h \in HF} |\bar{I}_{i,G}^h|^2 \leq I_{i,G}^n{}^2 \quad \forall i \in N \quad (13)$$

where $P_i^{f,G}$ and $Q_i^{f,G}$ are the active and RP generated by the CI-DRES at fundamental frequency f , V_i^f is the voltage of node i at f , and $I_{i,G}^n$ denotes the CI-DRES rated current.

Note that lower order HFVs have larger magnitude than higher HFVs. Hence, in order to compensate the lower-order HFV, larger $|\bar{I}_{i,G}^h|$ needs to be provided, e.g., $|\bar{I}_{i,G}^5| > |\bar{I}_{i,G}^7|$. Thus, in the term $\sum_{h \in HF} |\bar{I}_{i,G}^h|^2$ the largest share corresponds to the lowest order HF. For this reason, firstly, it is suggested that for $\forall i \in N$, the CR-DRES^h is computed per HF, resulting in four CR-DRES^h, for $h = 5, 7, 11, 13$. In some cases, this calculation might result into four different nodes and in other cases it might result to the same node. If the critical CI-DRES node is different per HF, it is proposed that **CR-DRES** is determined on the basis of the lowest order HFV to be compensated, i.e., CR-DRES⁵. This **CR-DRES** is the first one to reach its thermal limits, hence, it will have the highest “burden” or contribution to the harmonic mitigation as an AS. The second one to exhaust the thermal capacity will be CR-DRES⁷, etc.

D. Theoretical Framework based on the Harmonic Impedance Approach

Based on the above theoretical framework, in this subsection, an alternative approach to determine the **CR-DRES** is presented, i.e., the Harmonic Impedance approach at each HF. This approach is based on the sensitivity of the HFV with respect to the harmonic current injected at each node by a CI-DRES. The Y-Bus admittance matrix when the LV DN has i buses is represented as, [8]:

$$\mathbf{Y}_{\text{bus}} = \begin{bmatrix} y_{11} & \cdots & y_{1i} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ y_{i1} & \cdots & y_{ii} \end{bmatrix}_{i \times i} \quad (14)$$

By inverting this matrix, the network Z-bus matrix can be derived at every HF h . The harmonic impedance at each bus i with respect to harmonic current injection at bus j and harmonic \mathbf{h} ($\bar{H}I_{ij}^h$) is calculated as follows:

$$\bar{H}I_{ij}^h = \sum_{k \in \text{Path}_i \cap \text{Path}_j} \Re \{ \bar{Z}_{ik} \} + \mathbf{i} \sum_{k \in \text{Path}_i \cap \text{Path}_j} \Im \{ \bar{Z}_{ik} \} \cdot \mathbf{h} \quad (15)$$

where Path_i and Path_j denote the set of branches belonging to the path from the slack bus to buses i and j , respectively, while \bar{Z}_{ik} is the impedance of the line that directly connects bus i with bus k . The sensitivity of the HFV at node i , ∂V_i^h , to the harmonic current injection by a CI-DRES at node j , ∂I_j^h , can be evaluated by the absolute value of the harmonic impedance as:

$$\left| \frac{\partial V_i^h}{\partial I_j^h} \right| = \sqrt{(\Re \{ \bar{H}I_{ij}^h \})^2 + (\Im \{ \bar{H}I_{ij}^h \})^2} \quad (16)$$

It is evident, in this approach, that the loading of the lines and the respective harmonic currents are not needed for the calculation of the sensitivity, because the sensitivity depends only on the harmonic impedance; this simplifies the actions of the respective DNOs. In this case the critical CI-DRES per harmonic, CR-DRES^h can be calculated by:

$$\text{CR-DRES}^h = \text{MAX} \left[\sum_{\forall j \in N} \frac{\partial V_i^h}{\partial I_j^h} \right] \quad \forall i \in N \quad (17)$$

In a similar context as in the previous subsection, for a specific voltage variation, the smallest amount of ∂I^h will be provided by the CR-DRES^h. This corresponds to the smallest amount of $|\bar{I}_{i,G}^h|$ (the CI-DRES harmonic current injection at $HF = h$ and node i). It can be expected that the CR-DRES^h are different per harmonic. It should be noted that lower order HFVs have larger magnitude than higher HFVs. This means that in order to compensate the lower-order HFV, larger $|\bar{I}_{i,G}^h|$ is needed to be provided, e.g., $|\bar{I}_{i,G}^5| > |\bar{I}_{i,G}^7|$. In the sum of harmonic currents given by (13), the largest share corresponds to the lowest order HF. For this reason, after computing all CR-DRES^h for $h = 5, 7, 11, 13$, it is suggested that the most critical CI-DRES node, **CR-DRES** is determined to be CR-DRES⁵, i.e., the one that corresponds to the lowest order HFV to be compensated. This **CR-DRES** is the first one to reach its thermal limits, hence, it will have the highest “burden” or contribution to the harmonic mitigation as an AS. The second one to exhaust the thermal capacity will be CR-DRES⁷, etc.

The comparison of the approach given by (17) with the sensitivity analysis provided by (12) is demonstrated in Subsection V-C.

E. Quantification of CI-DRES contribution

The CI-DRES total daily contribution to the AF process can be quantified through the Fourier transform, as suggested in [51]:

$$D_{\text{day}} = \sqrt{\sum_{h=1}^{13} D_{h,\text{day}}^2} \quad (18)$$

$$D_{h,\text{day}} = \sum_{m=1}^{1440} [I_h(m) - I_f(m)\lambda_h], I_h(m) > I_f(m) \cdot \lambda_h \quad (19)$$

Fig. 1. Examined Topology of the IEEE European LV Test Feeder

Fig. 2. Examined Topology of the CIGRE European LV Residential DN

The actual contribution, $D_{h,day}$, of a CI-DRES over a day (1440 min) for the mitigation of the h -th harmonic is given in (18): $I_f(m)$ and $I_h(m)$ are the 1-min rms value of the fundamental current and harmonic current h respectively injected by the CI-DRES during the m th minute, and λ_h is the coefficient of individual HF, [34], e.g., $\lambda_h = 0.04$ for $h < 11$, $\lambda_h = 0.02$ for $11 \leq h < 17$, etc. Based on the 1-minute measurements of $I_f(m)$ and $I_h(m)$ for HFs 5, 7, 11 and 13, and the above sensitivity analyses it is expected that the **CR-DRES** will have the highest D_{day} value.

IV. SIMULATION MODELS

In this section the detailed simulation models are described for the: (i) TD simulations via PSIM software package, where

the virtual conductance method presented in [25] is applied; (ii) DHPFs in OpenDSS.

A. LV DN Models

Both types of simulations are conducted in two different benchmark LV DNs considering the following cases:

- two cases under a reduced version of the 416V (line-to-line) IEEE European LV Test Feeder, [38], [52] as illustrated in Fig. 1. The voltage at the slack bus is considered equal to 1.0675 p.u. same as in [38] at the FFPF, i.e., line-to-line voltage equal to 444.08V (while 1p.u. corresponds to 416V).
- two cases under a modified version of the CIGRE Task Force C6.04 European LV Residential DN, [53], of Fig. 2 are simulated - the cases are denoted in Fig. 2. The slack bus line-to-line voltage at the FFPF was taken equal to 400V.

In all the studied cases, the THD_V at some nodes is slightly less than 8% when the AHF control is deactivated. It is noted that the 8% limit is set by EN50160, and surpassing it may induce financial compensations by the DNO to the end-users at the specific nodes.

B. NLL Model

In the TD simulations, the NLLs are modelled as a 3-phase six-pulse diode bridges while the DC output of the bridge is C_{NL} parallel to R_{NL} . This NLL type has been chosen on purpose, because it causes high THD_V at $h = 5, 7, 11, 13$. In the CIGRE LV DN that is a relatively insensitive DN the values of the rectifier load are set to $C_{NL} = 1mF$ and $R_{NL} = 7.05\Omega$ leading to $P_{NL} = 40kW$ at $V_{NL} = 0.4kV$, while the NLL distortion power is $34kVAr$ at V_{NL} , i.e., comparable to its active power. At V_{NL} this NLL harmonic spectrum at the examined frequencies is shown in Table I. This NLL has been designed, so that the distortion is intentionally larger in the 5th and 7th HFs than in the typical 6-pulse NLL proposed in

Fig. 3. VSC topology and control

Fig. 4. Harmonics control - $k = -5, 7, -11, 13$ TABLE I
6-PULSE NLL HARMONIC CURRENT SPECTRUM

h	5	7	11	13
Magnitude, %	50	24	9.1	7.7

[37] and used in [17], [18]. In the IEEE LV DN the load of the rectifier is modified to $C_{NL} = 1.5mF$ and $R_{NL} = 7.5\Omega$ (leading to $P_{NL} = 42kW$ at $V_{NL} = 0.42kV$), because the previous values were causing a $THD_V > 8\%$.

C. CI-DRES Model

In the TD simulations the CI-DRES are modelled via the topology and local control structure of [25]. Specifically, the examined topology of the CI-DRES is a 3-phase 3-wire VSC with an LC filter (Fig. 3), [1], [25]. The voltage harmonic mitigation control strategy of [25] was developed in the frame of the H2020 project EASY-RES [54], along with the development of a prototype CI-DRES DC/AC VSC [55], and was designed to provide several AS, e.g., RP, virtual inertia, etc. The voltage harmonic mitigation is provided as long as there is available capacity with respect to the active and RP injection at the fundamental frequency, [51].

In this configuration, a three-level control scheme is adopted: Lower-Level Control to generate the PWM signals, Harmonic Control and Thermal Limit control. The reference

active (p^*) and RP (q^*) are employed to calculate the reference 1st harmonic ($i_{sd,1h}^*$, $i_{sq,1h}^*$) currents, as depicted in the blue box of Fig. 3. These currents are summed with the harmonic currents in dq frame and with the use of cascaded control in Fig. 3 the PWM signals η_d and η_q are generated and transformed to abc as η_{abc} . The Harmonics Control developed to generate the harmonic dq reference currents, $i_{dq,h}^*$, is illustrated in Fig. 4. The order of harmonics is denoted with the parameter k . This control has the aim of decomposing the harmonic voltages and currents of the VSC into different harmonics and then, compensate the low-order voltage harmonics 5th, 7th, 11th and 13th via the proper injection of respective harmonic currents. The decomposed signals $v_{dq,k-h}^*$, $v_{qg,k-h}^*$, for each harmonic k are transformed into the abc frame, $v_{abc,k-h}^*$, (Block 4 of Fig. 4) and are multiplied by a virtual conductance per HF G_k to generate the reference harmonic currents ($i_{abc,k-h}^*$), which are shifted 180° from the k voltage harmonic (Block 5).

The detailed calculation of the virtual conductance G_k per harmonic and the thermal capacity check with respect to the 1st harmonic are depicted in Fig. 5. Firstly, this block checks if there is capacity availability with respect to the 1st harmonic ($I_{rms}^{base} > I_{s,rms,1h}^*$). If there is no available capacity, G_k is set zero. If there is capacity, G control is activated. The value e_i is equal to $I_{rms}^{base} - I_{rms}^{total}$. In case there is capacity ($e_i > tol$),

 Fig. 5. Calculation of G_k based on Thermal Limit Control

G_k is increased. The term tol denotes that there is a tolerance zone around I_{rms}^{base} and has been taken equal to $0.5A$ (3% of the rated CI-DRES current). In case e_i lies within the tolerance zone, the value of G_k remains equal to the previous value G_{k-z} . By adding this zone, it is ensured that the harmonic currents and power do not oscillate. The initial value of G_k is set equal to a factor f_k per harmonic as given by:

$$f_k = \frac{h_k}{\sum_{k=5,7,11,13} h_k} \quad (20)$$

where h_k are the EN50160 limits of voltage distortion at nominal voltage, i.e. $h_5=6\%$, $h_7=5\%$, $h_{11}=3.5\%$ and $h_{13}=3\%$. In all cases that have been simulated with G control all the CI-DRES inject currents up to $I_{rms}^{base} - tol$, when they have available capacity. Further details with respect to the VSC topology and the detailed control scheme can be found in [25].

In all studied cases the CI-DRES active and RP are set to $10kW$ and 0 , respectively. The values of the current magnitudes and angles are calculated by the TD simulations, either in cases where the AHF control is activated or not. Then, these values are used as inputs in the DHPFs to evaluate the results in both simulation platforms.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, firstly, a comparison is performed with respect to the node voltages at each HF between: (i) the TD simulations via PSIM software package, where the virtual conductance method of [25] is activated (Cases denoted as “With Control”) or not (Cases denoted as “No Control”); (ii) by performing DHPFs in OpenDSS. Secondly, the existence of the “whack-a-mole” effect is discussed. Finally, the validity of the mathematical framework is assessed via the calculation of the sensitivity matrices when No AHF control is activated and the results of the TD simulations with respect to the current of each CI-DRES when the AHF control is activated.

A. Comparison between DHPFs and TD Simulations

In Figs. 6, 7 and 8 a comparison of the HFVs between the TD simulations and the DHPFs can be observed. The HFVs appear as a percentage of the line-to-line nominal

Fig. 6. Voltage HD per node and HFVs: Comparison between TD and DHPF in the Cigre LV DN - Case 2

Fig. 7. Voltage HD per node and HFVs: Comparison between TD and DHPF in the IEEE LV DN - Case 1

voltage (different for each LV DN). In the scenarios noted as “No Control” the CI-DRES AF is de-activated, while the scenarios “With Control” all CI-DRES participate in the harmonic mitigation via the virtual conductance approach.

In the CIGRE LV DN, the results concern Case 2 of Fig. 2 and the comparison is illustrated in Fig. 6. In all HFVs it can be noticed that: (a) the TD profiles at the different HFVs have larger values than the respective DHPFs, except at f . This is justified by the fact that in the DHPFs the slack bus voltage is

Fig. 8. Voltage HD per node and HFVs: Comparison between TD and DHPF in the IEEE LV DN - Case 2

zero and due to the frequency decoupling. However, in the TD simulations, the harmonic currents and the HFVs at different frequencies have a mutual coupling, as shown in the Appendix. This effect cannot be emulated in the DHPFs; (b) The previous condition leads to an almost “steady-state error” between the DHPFs and the TD simulations; however, the shape of the profiles is the same. This is especially important for the “No Control” cases where the sensitivity matrix is calculated; it means that the same results can be derived when using DHPFs instead of detailed models in the TD; (c) every individual HD_V is reduced with the control proposed in [25].

The IEEE European LV Test Feeder is more sensitive to power variations, and this is the reason it has been widely used in voltage quality studies, [38]. In this benchmark LV DN, the comparison between DHPFs and TD simulations is depicted in Figs. 7 and 8 for both Cases 1 and 2 of Fig. 1. Again, in these cases, in the DHPFs the slack bus voltage is zero due to the frequency decoupling and a steady-state error exists between the DHPFs and the TD simulations. Nevertheless, again, the shape of the profiles is the same, a really important issue, especially important for the “No Control” cases where the sensitivity matrix is calculated. Thereby, the same results can be derived when using DHPFs instead of detailed models in the TD.

B. Discussion on the Whack-a-mole Effect

In the IEEE LV DN, some interesting remarks are the following: (a) In Fig. 7 it can be observed that the control of [25] leads to the reduction of the 5th, 7th and 13th HFVs; in the 11th HF the voltage is increased, yet, it is below the pre-defined 3.5% limit; (b) When the mixture of NLLs/CI-DRES

Fig. 9. TD Simulations considering the activation of virtual conductance at specific HFVs in the IEEE LV DN - Case 2: (Top) HD_V per node and HF, (Bottom) THD_V per node

increases, in Fig. 8 it can be seen that the control of [25] leads to the reduction of the 5th and 11th HFVs, but in the 7th and 13th HFVs the voltages are increased - yet, they are below the pre-defined 5% and 3% limits respectively. In both cases, a “whack-a-mole” effect is evident, i.e., the mitigation of specific HFVs creates the outburst of other HFVs. This effect is usually met in higher voltage levels, where the π equivalents are used in the line impedance and can create resonances. In this specific LV DN, in both types of simulations the lines are modelled with $R-L$ elements. In the TD simulations the NLLs are 3-phase rectifiers with $R||C$ load at the DC side. The injection of specific harmonic currents by the CI-DRES can interact with the capacitors of the NLLs and the line impedances and create resonances, something that cannot be foreseen in advance, i.e., before the application of any AF control, if the CI-DRES harmonic current injection is not properly modelled in the DHPFs. Further research is needed towards the proper modelling of the CI-DRES AF capability in power flow tools. A working example on how HFVs at specific HFVs can exacerbate the harmonic line currents at specific HFVs with the existence of such NLLs appears in the Appendix.

Based on the results of Fig. 8 another round of TD simulations has been performed for Case 2, where the G_5 and G_{11}

TABLE II
SENSITIVITY MATRIX OF (12) FOR THE CIGRE CASE 1 AND $h=5$

NLL Node	CI-DRES Node		
	11	16	18
15	0.0052	0.0056	0.0059
17	0.0045	0.0043	0.0048

TABLE III
SENSITIVITY MATRIX OF (12) FOR THE CIGRE CASE 1 AND $h=7$

NLL Node	CI-DRES Node		
	11	16	18
15	0.013	0.013	0.014
17	0.010	0.010	0.010

TABLE IV
SENSITIVITY MATRIX OF (12) FOR THE CIGRE CASE 1 AND $h=11$

NLL Node	CI-DRES Node		
	11	16	18
15	0.133	0.142	0.145
17	0.111	0.115	0.116

TABLE V
SENSITIVITY MATRIX OF (12) FOR THE CIGRE CASE 1 AND $h=13$

NLL Node	CI-DRES Node		
	11	16	18
15	0.124	0.130	0.132
17	0.145	0.145	0.142

are activated, while G_7 and G_{13} are set to zero. Both G_5 and G_{11} take higher absolute values and larger respective harmonic currents are injected until the tolerance zone of Fig. 5 is reached. The achieved HD_V at each HF and the THD_V per node is shown in Fig. 9 with the light green line. It is evident that activating only G_5 and G_{11} can mitigate the respective HFVs most effectively, leading to an increase outbreak of the 7th and 13th HFVs. Still, the latter remain below the predefined limits. When the control is activated for all HFVs (purple line), the 5th and 11th HFVs are increased compared to the condition when only G_5 and G_{11} were activated, but the 7th and 13th HFVs are decreased. Consequently, the activation of all virtual conductances is the most promising solution for lower THD_V .

C. Validity of the Proposed Frameworks

1) *Results in the CIGRE LV DN*: Tables II-V show the results of the sensitivity analysis based on the Power Definition Approach for the CIGRE LV DN - Case 1. Tables VI-IX show the results of the respective sensitivity analysis for Case 2. The sensitivity matrices are calculated via (12) for each HF after performing DHPF under the “No Control” scenarios. In Fig. 10 the sum of the squares of the RMS currents (HFVs $h = 5, 7, 11, 13$ and f using (13)) in the TD simulations are illustrated for Cases 1 and 2. Note that the thermal limit of the CI-DRES is 18.1 A, and the limit of the tolerance zone is approximately 17.8A.

In Case 1 it can be derived based on (12) and Tables II-V that the highest sensitivity at $h = 5$ appears for the CI-DRES at Node 18 of Fig. 2, hence, this is the most critical CI-DRES at the 5th HF, CR-DRES⁵. The critical CI-DRES at $h = 7$, CR-DRES⁷ is again the CI-DRES at Node 18, the critical CI-DRES at $h = 11$, CR-DRES¹¹ is the CI-DRES at Node 18, while the critical CI-DRES at $h = 13$, CR-DRES¹³ is the CI-DRES at Node 16. Thus, based on the proposed framework the most critical CI-DRES, **CR-DRES**, at all HFVs is the CI-

Fig. 10. TD Simulation of the CIGRE LV DN - Sum of Harmonic Currents and Thermal Limit: (Top):Case 1, (Bottom):Case 2

DRES at Node 18, while the 2nd critical is the CI-DRES at Node 16 of Fig. 2. The validity of the proposed framework for Case 1 is demonstrated in Fig. 10-(Top); It is evident that CI-DRES 18 is the 1st to exhaust its thermal capacity, CI-DRES 16 is the 2nd, while CI-DRES 11 is the last one. This is in accordance with the proposed framework with the Power Definition Approach.

The same evaluation is performed for Case 2: it can be derived based on (12) and Tables VI-IX that for almost all HFVs, the CR-DRES appears to be the CI-DRES at Node 18 since it presented the maximum sum calculated by (12). The second CR-DRES at almost all HFVs is the CI-DRES at Node 9, which has the second largest sum at all HFVs. These are evident also in Fig. 10-(Bottom), where the CI-DRES at Nodes 18 and 9 almost simultaneously are the 1st ones to exhaust their thermal capacity. The CI-DRES at Node 16 is the 2nd one, the CI-DRES at Node 14 is 3rd and the CI-DRES at Node 11 is the last one. These results are also in accordance with the framework based on the Power Definition Approach.

In addition, the results of the sensitivity analysis based on the Harmonic Impedance approach are shown in Tables X-XIII. In this approach, the calculation of the sensitivity matrix is much easier, since it is based only on the impedances at each HF, which are already known to the DNOs without requiring any knowledge on the specific loading conditions. It can be derived by summing the elements of the Tables, that the highest sensitivity is calculated for the CI-DRES at Node 18, then for the CI-DRES at Node 9, etc., following again the sequence of Fig. 10 for both Cases in the CIGRE LV DN. Consequently, both types of sensitivity calculations can be used either for the evaluation of decentralized APF methods and the CI-DRES contribution per harmonic. Nevertheless, the Harmonic Impedance approach requires no prior knowledge of the loading conditions and has less computational burden.

2) *Result in the IEEE European LV DN*: In this section the results in the IEEE European LV DN are presented considering only the Harmonic Impedance approach due to its aforementioned advantages. The results of the sensitivity matrix calculation based on (17) appears in Tables XIV-XVII. It can be clearly observed that the highest sum at each HF

TABLE VI
SENSITIVITY MATRIX OF (12) FOR THE CIGRE CASE 2 AND $h=5$

NLL Node	CI-DRES Node				
	9	11	14	16	18
6	0.0056	0.0052	0.0051	0.0048	0.0057
10	0.0036	0.0040	0.0037	0.0039	0.0034
15	0.0059	0.0016	0.0052	0.0057	0.0060
17	0.0036	0.0036	0.0040	0.0039	0.0037

TABLE VII
SENSITIVITY MATRIX OF (12) FOR THE CIGRE CASE 2 AND $h=7$

NLL Node	CI-DRES Node				
	9	11	14	16	18
6	0.0265	0.0250	0.0246	0.0253	0.0266
10	0.0185	0.0183	0.0186	0.0188	0.0182
15	0.0297	0.0105	0.0273	0.0290	0.0297
17	0.0184	0.0182	0.0185	0.0187	0.0186

TABLE VIII
SENSITIVITY MATRIX OF (12) FOR THE CIGRE CASE 2 AND $h=11$

NLL Node	CI-DRES Node				
	9	11	14	16	18
6	0.0618	0.0592	0.0603	0.0605	0.0620
10	0.0477	0.048	0.049	0.0492	0.0471
15	0.0580	0.038	0.057	0.0575	0.0581
17	0.0478	0.0482	0.0494	0.0492	0.0481

TABLE IX
SENSITIVITY MATRIX OF (12) FOR THE CIGRE CASE 2 AND $h=13$

NLL Node	CI-DRES Node				
	9	11	14	16	18
6	0.156	0.151	0.150	0.153	0.156
10	0.116	0.114	0.116	0.116	0.115
15	0.156	0.150	0.152	0.155	0.157
17	0.116	0.115	0.117	0.117	0.117

TABLE X
SENSITIVITY MATRIX OF (17) FOR CIGRE LV DN AND $h=5$

NLL Node	CI-DRES Node				
	9	11	14	16	18
6	0.14	0.094	0.109	0.14	0.14
10	0.186	0.094	0.109	0.14	0.201
15	0.11	0.094	0.1853	0.109	0.109
17	0.186	0.094	0.109	0.14	0.186

TABLE XI
SENSITIVITY MATRIX OF (17) FOR CIGRE LV DN AND $h=7$

NLL Node	CI-DRES Node				
	9	11	14	16	18
6	0.1931	0.1308	0.1515	0.1931	0.1931
10	0.2556	0.1308	0.1515	0.1931	0.2765
15	0.1515	0.1308	0.2376	0.1515	0.1515
17	0.2556	0.1308	0.1515	0.1931	0.2556

TABLE XII
SENSITIVITY MATRIX OF (17) FOR CIGRE LV DN AND $h=11$

NLL Node	CI-DRES Node				
	9	11	14	16	18
6	0.3010	0.2047	0.2368	0.1397	0.1397
10	0.3974	0.2047	0.2368	0.1397	0.2011
15	0.2368	0.2047	0.3503	0.109	0.109
17	0.3974	0.2047	0.2368	0.1397	0.1857

TABLE XIII
SENSITIVITY MATRIX OF (17) FOR CIGRE LV DN AND $h=13$

NLL Node	CI-DRES Node				
	9	11	14	16	18
6	0.3551	0.2418	0.2795	0.3551	0.3551
10	0.4686	0.2418	0.2795	0.3551	0.5065
15	0.2795	0.2418	0.4085	0.2795	0.2795
17	0.4686	0.2418	0.2795	0.3551	0.4686

appears for the CI-DRES at Node 681, the second highest for

Fig. 11. TD Simulation of the IEEE LV DN - Sum of Harmonic Currents and Thermal Limit: (Top):Case 1, (Bottom):Case 2

TABLE XIV
SENSITIVITY MATRIX OF (17) FOR IEEE LV DN AND $h=5$

NLL Node	CI-DRES Node				
	387	388	476	619	681
342	0.1134	0.1159	0.1159	0.1159	0.1159
406	0.1134	0.1190	0.1414	0.1414	0.1414
639	0.1134	0.1190	0.1855	0.2205	0.2145
682	0.1134	0.1190	0.1855	0.2138	0.2138

TABLE XV
SENSITIVITY MATRIX OF (17) FOR IEEE LV DN AND $h=7$

NLL Node	CI-DRES Node				
	387	388	476	619	681
342	0.1395	0.1424	0.1424	0.1424	0.1424
406	0.1395	0.146	0.1702	0.1702	0.1702
639	0.1395	0.146	0.2177	0.2556	0.2491
682	0.1395	0.146	0.2177	0.2484	0.2484

TABLE XVI
SENSITIVITY MATRIX OF (17) FOR IEEE LV DN AND $h=11$

NLL Node	CI-DRES Node				
	387	388	476	619	681
342	0.1983	0.2022	0.2022	0.2022	0.2022
406	0.1983	0.2069	0.2364	0.2364	0.2364
639	0.1983	0.2069	0.2940	0.3397	0.3319
682	0.1983	0.2069	0.2940	0.331	0.331

TABLE XVII
SENSITIVITY MATRIX OF (17) FOR IEEE LV DN AND $h=13$

NLL Node	CI-DRES Node				
	387	388	476	619	681
342	0.2292	0.2337	0.2337	0.2337	0.2337
406	0.2292	0.2391	0.2718	0.2718	0.2718
639	0.2292	0.2391	0.3353	0.3857	0.3771
682	0.2292	0.2391	0.3353	0.3761	0.3761

the CI-DRES at Node 619, followed by the CI-DRES at Nodes 476, 388 and 387. The TD simulations for Cases 1 and 2 in the IEEE European LV DN, as illustrated in Fig. 11, reveal the validity of the proposed framework, since for both Cases the CI-DRES at Node 387 is the last to reach the thermal limit (hence, it is the least critical), while the most critical one is the CI-DRES 681 in Case 2.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

In this paper the mathematical framework for voltage harmonic sensitivity analysis is used to analyze the contribution of each CI-DRES in the decentralized harmonic filtering process,

Fig. 12. Simple Grid configuration with 3-phase rectifier as NLL.

with the presence of NLLs within the DN based on CI-DRES location and available capacity. The available capacity is an important element since, in the future, the CI-DRES may supply many services at the same time, such as reactive power or virtual inertia. The sensitivity analysis is performed with two approaches, which can derive the same results with respect to the proper selection of the CI-DRES to perform APF. It is noted that the Harmonic Impedance approach requires no knowledge on the loading conditions and exhibits less computational burden. The mathematical framework for quantifying the CI-DRES contribution is validated using time domain simulations and decoupled harmonic power flows in two benchmark European DNs with varied CI-DRES/NLL mixtures. Despite the fact that the DHPFs miss the harmonic frequency coupling, both simulation types reveal the same trend with respect to the voltage harmonic distortion. Thus, the DHPFs can be safely used by the DNOs for such studies with less computational burden than TD simulations. In addition, insights on the practical implementation of the framework are discussed. The acquired conclusions pave the way for the development of a new distributed harmonic mitigation strategy based on the sensitivity matrix at each harmonic. If considering the harmonic mitigation process, DNOs could potentially use the proposed framework for CI-DRES sizing during the planning stage. Future research will also focus on the proper modelling of NLLs and CI-DRES as APFs in HPF tools like Open-DSS and unbalanced conditions of the LV DNs via suitable unbalanced HPF models. This will lead to a new coordinated AHF control approach at DN level. Finally, based on the proposed framework, active filtering can be regarded as a new AS to be supplied by CI-DRES at the DN level and introduced in relevant markets.

APPENDIX

The virtual conductance approach examined in this paper is based on the injection of harmonic currents that are proportional to each specific HFV. Hence, the injection of such currents in 3-phase rectifiers (with $R_d||C_d$ load at the DC side) can be evaluated indirectly by examining the effect of the existence of the respective HFV. Due to the nature of the rectifiers, such HFV can increase the harmonic content of the line currents, which can further create HFVs at other nodes (PCC) where other devices are connected. The examined configuration appears in Fig. 12. Here, it is assumed that: firstly, such rectifier operates at a single node and is fed via a purely 1st HF sinusoidal voltage ((21)-(23)); secondly, a 5th HF sinusoidal voltage is added to the node considering different values $x\% \cdot 230V$ with respect to its RMS voltage,

Fig. 13. Influence of the 5th HFV (magnitude x , % and angle φ_a) on the 7th and 13th harmonic currents absorbed by a NLL: (Left) 7th HD_I and (Right) 13th HD_I .

i.e., 0% (only fundamental frequency), 2%, 3% and 5% ((21)-(26)). In addition, the effect of the voltage angle φ_a of the 5th HFV is examined, i.e., 0°, 30°, 60° and 90°. Note that the 5th HF is in the negative sequence.

$$V_{1a} = 230 \cdot \sqrt{2} \cdot \sin(2\pi 5ft) \quad (21)$$

$$V_{1b} = 230 \cdot \sqrt{2} \cdot \sin(2\pi 5ft - 120) \quad (22)$$

$$V_{1c} = 230 \cdot \sqrt{2} \cdot \sin(2\pi 5ft - 240) \quad (23)$$

$$V_{5a} = x\% \cdot 230 \cdot \sqrt{2} \cdot \sin(2\pi 5ft + \varphi_a) \quad (24)$$

$$V_{5b} = x\% \cdot 230 \cdot \sqrt{2} \cdot \sin(2\pi 5ft + \varphi_a - 240) \quad (25)$$

$$V_{5c} = x\% \cdot 230 \cdot \sqrt{2} \cdot \sin(2\pi 5ft + \varphi_a - 120) \quad (26)$$

The simulations are performed in PSIM Software Package. The effect of 5th HFV was particularly evident on the individual HD of the line currents HD_I at the 7th and 13th HF, which are positive sequence harmonics. The respective results of the are shown in Fig. 13. It is observed that the injection of the 5th HFV at $\varphi_a > 30^\circ$ can exacerbate the HD_I at the 7th and 13th HF that are injected at the PCC. These harmonic currents can further increase the respective HFVs at different nodes of the LV DN.

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